

WAYS TO INTEREST AND TEACH PRESCHOOL CHILDREN IN A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract. This article describes the methodology of teaching English to preschool children, which is the main link of continuous education. Also, several instructions are given on interactive methods, requirements for teachers and improving the effectiveness of the lesson. Effects, effectiveness, easy and convenient methods of language learning in preschool children are shown.

Keywords: preschool children, educators, English language, various interesting games, interesting and effective methods, cartoons. Poems in English.

СПОСОБЫ ЗАИНТЕРЕСОВАТЬ И ОБУЧИТЬ ДОШКОЛЬНИКОВ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ

Аннотация. В данной статье описывается методика обучения английскому языку детей дошкольного возраста, которая является основным звеном непрерывного образования. Также дано несколько указаний по интерактивным методам, требованиям к учителям и повышению эффективности урока. Показаны эффекты, эффективность, простые и удобные методы изучения языка у детей дошкольного возраста.

Ключевые слова: дошкольники, воспитатели, английский язык, различные интересные игры, интересные и эффективные методики, мультфильмы. Стихи на английском языке.

INTRODUCTION

After our country gained independence, interest in teaching foreign languages increased and many opportunities were created for young people. This is certainly not for nothing. There is no need to overestimate the importance of perfect knowledge of foreign languages for our countries, which are striving to take their rightful place in the world community today, and for our people, who are building their great future in solidarity and cooperation with our foreign partners. That nowadays in our country a lot of attention is paid to the English language. There is a person who seeks knowledge from birth to the end of his life. Currently, 80 percent of the world's countries are conducting scientific research on language learning and teaching in their field of education. Among these, one of the most urgent issues is to interest preschool children in the English language. As our ancestors used to say, "Knowing a language means knowing a hand." Language is a symbol of society. Therefore, learning a language from an early age is equal to learning many countries and societies. Even in this case, UNESCO has been significantly showing its place in language learning to the young generation by its actions. Also, young children are distinguished by the fact that they acquire their world views and thinking skills through language. This indicates that they are getting an effective education.

Despite the fact that children of preschool age have a lot of love and desire for science, they differ in their brain activity. Deep thinking - through the ability to think deeply, it helps to increase

the worldview and speed of brain activity. The more languages a child learns, the more their thinking and analytical and synthesis abilities of the brain will increase.

Working through visual aids, posters and books.

Primary school students in rural areas usually grow up far away from the English language environment, and children's thinking remains abstract, and the process of acquiring new knowledge is always based on emotions. Therefore, English teachers of kindergarten age make full use of materials around students, flashcards, and other teaching aids in teaching through easy methods. As we all know, learning and teaching the language with methods provides many facilities for science. This makes it possible for us to teach quickly and at the right time, without difficulties, in a certain pattern. There are many principles of language teaching nowadays, including:

1. Hearing method
2. The method of using visual textbooks
3. Game method
4. Poem memorization method

Various musics and audios are used in this. For example, if the given topic is about letters, they will hear and repeat the letters through the audio broadcast.

Use of multimedia to improve teaching effectiveness.

Teaching through multimedia gives great opportunities to the teacher. In this way, it is possible to raise the interest of children to a high level and to attract their attention for a long time. Through this, we can see that children's language skills have increased again.

The visual principle is also related to this method, it is shown through the screen or through the teacher's hand movements, and they find it by looking at the words they hear. In addition, they will conduct a broadcast lesson along with watching the video.

The method of learning the language with games is one of the most common methods and is used in almost all countries of the world. The main goal in learning foreign languages is to memorize words. This game is a basket full of artificial vegetables that the children pick up one by one and say their names in English. Poem memorization method is one of the most common and productive method, which is mainly useful for memorizing lyrics. If we consider this as an example in one language, you will have a clearer understanding through this. For example, when we ask young children how many days are in the month, they almost always get confused.

Using songs and action games to improve the classroom environment.

Creating a flexible classroom atmosphere is sometimes more important than any teaching method. In the class, at the beginning of the lesson, all the children, led by the teacher, sang a song together with a nice English song and danced a little to its tune. This in itself will help them exercise their bodies, become more energetic and memorize the lyrics of the song faster. The English environment, importantly, allows for a natural entry into a good learning atmosphere. Therefore, by memorizing the following verse, they will have full knowledge and understanding. "Thirty days have September, "Thirty days have September,

Thirty days has September,
April, June, and November,
All the rest have thirty-one,
But February's twenty-eight,

The leap year, which comes once in four gives February one day more.

All these principles are considered to be very effective and useful, and are currently being applied to all preschool children.

Using puzzle games to reinforce acquired skills.

It is necessary to increase the child's interest in the English language from a young age, it is necessary to force him to speak even if there is a mistake, only then the child can overcome the obstacles in front of him and speak without fear. If we make a foreign language lesson not a lesson, but a game, it will increase the interest of young children. At the same time, their level of activity also increases. The most important thing is that every preschool educational institution has multilingual trainers. A number of researches conducted on young children show that the representative of one nationality learns the language of the representative of another nationality without difficulty, freely and friendly through the actions, gestures and pronunciation of the representative of that nationality. And this creates convenience for young children. It serves for them to organize the language without fear or hesitation. It means that our future is bright and shiny. Education is the future! In Uzbekistan, the age of education starts at the age of 3. "Children between the ages of 3 and 7 are admitted to public kindergartens. The age and order of admission to private kindergartens are determined independently by these kindergartens." - Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The goal of getting children interested in science from an early age and developing their mental abilities is put forward, and the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev Miromonovich, pays attention to the young generation and creates facilities for it. The president is creating opportunities for free education and its promotion. The relevance of the topic is that early education means opening new doors for the future. Especially in younger children, the strength of memory is different compared to older children. For example, young children learning a second language can learn a second language quickly and easily due to the speed of their brains. That's why the implementation of education from an early age is considered the main goal and is being implemented.

Reasons why the educator is not able to achieve the desired results.

Failure of the teacher to ask the children questions and answers correctly. Too many preschoolers are quiet and very dismissive of things they don't like. Overcoming this requires a lot of effort from the educator, the questions he asks should show the wisdom of the educator and that he has taken this topic very seriously. When we worked with children, we found out that children's intuitive learning is much higher than ours, that is, that of adults. They can't express it, but they feel it, and they show it with their own actions. We usually divide the question. By removing the barriers between the student and the teacher, the student can find a way to the heart of the children. They will need to start questioning with a sense of politeness.

Conclusion

In short, the main goal is to teach young children foreign languages from an early age in an effective way and to make them interested in the language through interesting games - this will help them learn the language quickly and easily. This will serve as a support for them to become children and representatives of the great future.

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